

DISCLOSURE OF THIRD PARTY FUNDERS IN INTERNATIONAL ARBITRATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This thesis is devoted to highlighting some issues related to third-party financing in international arbitrations, in particular, the disclosure of third-party financing to disputing parties and arbitrators, the principles of transparency and impartiality, real cases related to the industry, and specific advantages and disadvantages of third-party financing.

Third-party financing means the activities of third parties not related to the subject of the dispute, which are aimed at taking over all court costs for the parties involved in the case, and in return receive a certain percentage of the winnings in the dispute. In some cases, the financing party completely "buys" the dispute from the plaintiff, that is, the financed party loses almost its independence in the case and is limited to presenting relevant documents to the court. The financing third party will deal with the rest of the processes. This, of course, is one of the manifestations of third-party financing.

Example of Third-Party Litigation Financing for Plaintiffs

Source: GAO. | GAO-23-105210

This type of financing is mainly used by plaintiffs and in some cases also by defendants. Funding third parties are mostly involved in cases where counterclaims are filed by the defendant.

Disclosure of the identity of financing third parties to the parties and arbitrators is one of the topics that is causing extensive discussions today. Mandatory disclosure of the identity of the financier and related information is

cited as the main requirement. Below we will get acquainted with the practice of prestigious international arbitration centers related to this issue.

The International Chamber of Commerce (ICC) was found as one of the most preferred courts according to the results of the 2021 survey¹. This chamber has been gradually implementing reforms related to third-party financing for a long time. In particular, in 2015, in the Chamber's "Decision on International Arbitration Costs", the Tribunal is given the right to disclose them in order to determine the existence of third-party financiers. In addition, it is necessary for the arbitrators to be aware of any parties interested in the material value to be collected in order to resolve the dispute impartially and fairly. In 2021, according to the newly adopted Article 11(7), the disclosure of financiers is defined as mandatory:

"The Secretariat must be duly notified by the parties about any third parties who have a material interest in the dispute"².

If we consider the practice of the **Singapore International Arbitration Center (SIAC)**, it is one of the first arbitration centers in Asia to introduce the practice of third-party financing. Requirements related to the disclosure of financiers have arisen in this arbitration since 2017. According to it, the identity of the financiers, their interest in resolving the dispute, awareness of potential expenses not foreseen in the case will be clarified.

The experience of the **Hong Kong International Arbitration Center (HKIAC)** has been to implement such measures since 2018. According to Article 44 of the relevant arbitration regulation, the financed party must submit a written statement about its financier to the other parties to the dispute and to the arbitrators. The identity of the financier and the terms of the agreement on the structure with him should be stated in the notice.

In the practice of the **Dubai International Arbitration Center (DIAC)**, the issue of disclosure of third-party financiers was regulated in 2022, according to which financiers must be disclosed immediately and the agreement between them and the parties must be explained to the arbitrators and the opposing party.

In the **International Center for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID)**, this practice was regulated for the first time in 2022. According to Article 14 of the 2022 ICSID Arbitration Rules, disputing parties have an

¹ Twelfth empirical study of the School of International Arbitration, Queen Mary University of London, in partnership with White & Case LLP.

² The 2021 ICC Arbitration Rules: clarity, efficiency and technology // URL: [https://www.gide.com/en/news/the-2021-icc-arbitration-rules-clarity-efficiency-and-technology#:~:text=Similarly%2C%20article%2011\(7\),the%20enforceability%20of%20the%20award.](https://www.gide.com/en/news/the-2021-icc-arbitration-rules-clarity-efficiency-and-technology#:~:text=Similarly%2C%20article%2011(7),the%20enforceability%20of%20the%20award.)

obligation to disclose third-party funds (including the name and address of the funder) to avoid conflicts of interest that may arise from such financial arrangements³. The parties must disclose this information immediately after filing a Request for Arbitration or entering into a Third Party Funding Agreement. In addition, the court may order disclosure of additional information regarding third-party financiers at any stage of the proceedings.

At the **Vienna International Arbitration Center (VIAC)**, these rules will be adopted in 2021, and if the court deems it necessary, the regulation of financing, the financier's interest in the outcome of the litigation and/or whether or not the financier has taken its obligation or not, may order the disclosure of information⁴.

As can be seen from the latest developments, the rules related to the regulation of third-party financing and its disclosure to the parties are becoming more and more popular and are gradually being reflected in many arbitrations. However, against the background of this trend, there are also opinions against the regulation of third-party financing in a separate order. For example, proposals have recently been made in the UK to revise the Arbitration Act of 1996. However, a proposal to amend the law to regulate third-party financing was rejected by the Law Commission. This is because, according to the Commission, parties can already choose arbitration rules containing such provisions if they are important to them, and the arbitrator already has factors that cast doubt on the impartiality of the arbitrator, obliged to inform.

Nevertheless, as the volume of disputes around the world increases and companies face significant financial difficulties in handling their claims, the increasing trend of mandatory disclosure of third-party financing to parties and arbitrators should be accepted as a natural development of the international arbitration structure. The adoption of such rules will solve important issues related to conflict of interest and confidentiality, and will take the first steps towards transparency between the parties and the court.

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2. The 2021 ICC Arbitration Rules: clarity, efficiency and technology // URL: <https://www.gide.com/en/news/the-2021-icc-arbitration-rules-clarity-efficiency-and->

³ [ICSID Arbitration Rules](https://icsid.worldbank.org/rules-regulations/convention/arbitration-rules/introductory-note), 2022, // <https://icsid.worldbank.org/rules-regulations/convention/arbitration-rules/introductory-note>

⁴ VIAC Rules of Arbitration and mediation 2021, // <https://www.viac.eu/en/arbitration/content/vienna-rules-2021-online>

